

Author: Maher Jarjour

Title: Updates (Further Evidence) on The Universe Formation Paper

On May 28th, 2022, I published a research “[Theory and preliminary Evidence of Universe Formation and Our Life Patterns in Relation to That Formation](#)” which consists of a theory proposes that the universe formed with magnetic fields, chemistry, space, and time, It also proposes how we are related to this formation. I was keeping an eye on the latest related space and science discoveries, and I identified various further probable evidence. I thought about publishing this update that included results and mapping the results of both papers hoping it can help reveal new areas to research on how we came into existence, and where life elsewhere could exist.

- The magnetic fields could have been the first thing that happened in universe formation when the universe was probably dark, through a [simulation](#) (1) by researchers from the University of Hamburg.
- Scientists were able create particle-[antiparticle](#) (15) pairs from nothing at strong enough electromagnetic fields in a [simple laboratory setup](#) (2).
- A research [paper by Columbia scientists](#) (10) offers insight show that magnetic fields may spontaneously arise in turbulent plasma, and that turbulence of those plasmas can also amplify magnetic fields to spread to vast distances.
- The [water on Saturn Enceladus](#) (3) could have formed on the outer side of the accretion disk that formed Saturn if Saturn formation started or assisted by the magnetic fields. [Enceladus](#) (16) may have formed later as a moon after a celestial body, or bodies hit the outer side of Saturn during the end of its formation.
- Mg-Phosphate was found on Bennu (101955) analyzed sample, which could be an important recorder of aqueous activity on the parent body. I mentioned in my paper that scientists found nucleobases in the meteorites that made their way to earth during the [formation of the solar system](#) (17). This means those nucleobases may have existed along with water on the meteorites that originated from asteroids such as asteroid 101955. The related article was [published by NASA](#) (4).
- Scientists found ancient rocks that hold evidence earth magnetic fields were strong billions of years ago, and that the mechanism driving earth's early dynamo was similarly efficient to the solidification process that generates earth's magnetic field today. [This study](#) (5) was performed by researchers from the University of Oxford.
- Scientists found that [300 solar-mass first-generation star](#) (6) may have dispersed a unique mixture of heavy [elements](#) (13) across interstellar space, which happened over time and across the cosmos.
- I came across an article by researchers from the University of Bristol that coincides with parts in my universe formation theory paper. [The article says](#) (7) that everything alive today derives from a common ancestor known affectionately as Luca. Within a few hundred years of planetary formation [life on earth](#) (20) was already flourishing. Researchers hypothesized that all forms of life start from single celled organisms to gigantic trees, including humans.
- Researchers have developed a [remote, non-invasive method](#) (8) of selectively controlling neurons in the brain using magnetic fields, which coincide with my theory.

- Scientists used a [specific MRI design](#) (9) in an experiment and found that our brains may have quantum functions.

I mentioned in a previous [Linkedin post](#) a few months ago, the story of the inspiration that helped me to develop the idea of the original paper from human perspective into space. The original theory and the further updates and evidence may suggest that magnetic fields existed when the universe was dark (No stars, Galaxies, or planets) and through time (Billions of years) and space that existed. The magnetic fields [helped to form](#) (12) the first [accretion disk](#) (11) (Probably very colossal), then first stars, planets, and [galaxies](#) (21). Planets and their [composition](#) (19), may have formed with the assistance of magnetic fields and [accretion disk](#) (18) process. Our brains may have developed with the evolution of the universe from its very beginning.

Universe Evolution (Billions of years)

The universe was probably dark for millions or billions of years

The collage features several key elements:

- Left side:** A vertical strip of six purple and blue images showing magnetic field patterns.
- Center-left:** Two diagrams labeled (A) and (B) illustrating the Stretch-Twist-Fold mechanism for magnetic field amplification.
- Center:** A vertical strip of four images showing the formation of a protostar and its accretion disk.
- Center-right:** A large image of a protoplanetary disk with several planets forming.
- Right side:** A vertical strip of images showing various galaxy types, including spiral and elliptical galaxies.
- Bottom right:** A map of the world showing the distribution of meteorites, labeled 'WORLD METEORITE DISTRIBUTION'.

Magnetic fields may spontaneously arise in turbulent plasma (10). Turbulence of those plasmas can also amplify magnetic fields to spread to vast (10) distances. The Stretch-Twist-Fold mechanism results in twice the magnetic field one started with and leads to exponential (1) amplification in time. Accretion disk may start.

First stars form from giant clouds of dust and gas gravitational (11) collapse, turbulent motion, and magnetic fields (12).

Earliest stars were so colossally huge that when they died as supernova, they tore themselves apart, dispersing a unique mixture of heavy elements across interstellar space(6).

At least one supernova (13) must have exploded near the still-forming solar system (14) to create the radioactive elements seen in ancient meteorites.

Water (4) and other elements were (3) delivered to the solar(16) system via meteorites (17).

Galaxies formed around pockets of space that were slightly denser than their (21) surroundings.

Prepared by Maher Jarjour (Images credits mentioned and related to the accompanied paper).

- References;

- 1, <https://science-chatter.blogs.uni-hamburg.de/?p=340>
- 2, <https://bigthink.com/starts-with-a-bang/something-from-nothing/>
- 3, <https://www.jameswebbdiscovery.com/discoveries/webb-maps-surprisingly-large-plume-jetting-from-saturns-moon-enceladus>
- 4, https://ntrs.nasa.gov/api/citations/20240000339/downloads/BarnesEtAl_LPSC2024_OREX_phosphates_1532.pdf
- 5, <https://www.ox.ac.uk/news/2024-04-24-researchers-find-oldest-undisputed-evidence-earth-s-magnetic-field>
- 6, <https://scitechdaily.com/after-many-years-of-searching-potential-first-traces-of-the-universes-earliest-stars-discovered/>
- 7, <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2024/07/240712124116.htm>
- 8, https://newatlas.com/health-wellbeing/magnetogenetic-social-behavior-appetite/?utm_source=substack&utm_medium=email
- 9, <https://phys.org/news/2022-10-brains-quantum.amp>
- 10, <https://scitechdaily.com/turbulent-plasma-uncovering-the-source-of-the-universes-magnetic-fields/>
- 11, <https://www.universetoday.com/135153/first-detailed-image-accretion-disk-around-young-star/>
- 12, <https://pweb.cfa.harvard.edu/news/role-magnetic-fields-star-formation-0>
- 13, <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/our-sun-was-born-in-a-stellar-family-far-far-from-here/>
- 14, <https://www.jameswebbdiscovery.com/hobbies/astrophotography/the-ultimate-guide-to-solar-system-imagers-for-capturing-the-cosmos>
- 15, <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/stars-made-of-antimatter-might-be-lurking-in-the-universe/>
- 16, <https://www.planetary.org/articles/signs-of-life-enceladus>
- 17, https://www.universetoday.com/165165/the-meteorites-that-made-earth-were-filled-with-water/#google_vignette
- 18, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Earth/Effects-of-planetesimal-impacts>
- 19, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2009.04311>
- 20, <https://opengeology.org/historicalgeology/a-brief-history-of-earth/>
- 21, <https://science.nasa.gov/universe/galaxies/evolution/#intro>